

DNRF CoARA action plan 2026-2030

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Introduction

This action plan describes the implementation of initiatives to promote responsible research assessment at the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF) in the period 2026-2030.

To provide context, this action plan outlines the aims of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and the DNRF's aims and current assessment model.

In October 2022, the DNRF signed ARRA, involving the drawing up of a five-year action plan, and joined the coalition of signatories (CoARA).

The DNRF strongly supports the aims of ARRA and acknowledges the role of research foundations in propagating an academic culture that promotes research quality and assesses research in a fair manner.

The DNRF finds that these objectives align very closely with its long-standing tradition. This action plan describes how the DNRF will further develop its assessment processes in the coming years, and how this relates to the Foundation's current aims and practices.

The DNRF's purpose and assessment practice

The Danish National Research Foundation was established in 1991 with the objective of strengthening the development of Danish research by funding outstanding basic research at the highest international level in all scientific disciplines. The main mechanism for achieving this objective is to fund relatively large research centers - Centers of Excellence - across the academic spectrum, typically for a period of ten years.

Research is assessed on the following occasions:

- Applications for grants (two stages)
- Annual reporting and follow-up meetings
- Midterm and final evaluations
- Evaluations of the Foundation itself.

Dialogue and interaction are cornerstones of the DNRF's continual monitoring and follow-up procedure. Once a year, 1-2 board members and the secretariat visit each Center of Excellence for a two-and-a-half-hour status meeting. The primary aim of the meeting is to engage in constructive dialogue concerning the center's scientific progress. This close, trust-based di-

alogue promotes honesty and allows the Foundation to support the centers in a pragmatic and flexible manner.

The Foundation carries out a formal (stop/go) evaluation of each center after five years. These evaluations also involve direct dialogue and qualitative assessment by the Foundation board, underpinned by external reviews and self-assessments.

Transparency is a high priority in this process. As such, when an evaluation makes use of external reviewers, the applicants may comment on the list of potential reviewers and respond to their reports.

Each assessment of an application to become a Center of Excellence focuses on four main elements: idea, leadership, team, and organization. Bibliometric measures play a limited role in relation to the board's assessments of individual researchers or applications. The use of JIF scores has been discontinued.

The DNRF approach to assessment thus conforms with ARRA objectives and adheres to international standards concerning research integrity, Open Science, and FAIR data.

Former actions and the DNRF strategy 2026-2030

Since signing the ARRA agreement in 2022, the DNRF has:

- Engaged in discussions with and drawn inspiration from other Danish foundations as part of an informal network driven by Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF), the VILLUM Foundation and Aalborg University. This informal network is now a national chapter under CoARA.
- Changed the CV format of pre-proposals to promote the display of broader sets of experiences and skills of the suggested core team members.
- Held dialogue with all its grant holders about their perspectives on responsible research assessment.
- Concluded an extensive 360-degree evaluation process, in accordance with CoARA principles.
- Consulted with the grant holders and with a broader group of stakeholders in the Danish research landscape about the foundation's tentative strategic priorities in relation to research assessment, among other topics.

The DNRF has also announced a number of new initiatives as part of its strategic priorities for 2026-2030, as announced on February 20, 2026, including the promotion of responsible research assessment, which is one of three key strategic priorities. As a consequence, the Foundation will launch the following initiatives in 2026:

- An adjusted CV format for second-stage full applications, building on experiences from other foundations, specifically the Independent Research Fund Denmark
- The exploration of new models for assessing research proposals, including a pilot scheme for including 'peer advisers' in the assessment process
- The further enhancement of the DNRF's unique monitoring and follow-up model, involving dialogue with and support for grant holders.

This action plan will be implemented between 2026 and 2030, following the timeline of the DNRF strategy.

Status and initiatives according to individual ARRA commitments

Commitment	Status	New initiatives	Expected initiation
<p>Core commitment 1</p> <p>Recognize the diversity of contributions to and careers in research, in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.</p>	<p>The DNRF assessment of new grant and extension applications focuses on the experiences of both leaders and teams, as well as complementarities, in a way that takes into account the collective set of experiences, skills and competences required for center progress.</p>	<p>Adjusted CV formats are being introduced, drawing inspiration from the CV formats and responsible research assessment considerations of other foundations.</p>	<p>An adjusted CV format for preproposals was introduced with the call for the 13th round of Centers of Excellence (February 27, 2026).</p> <p>An adjusted CV format will be introduced for second-round applicants in January 2027.</p>
<p>Core commitment 2</p> <p>Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.</p> <p>and</p> <p>Core commitment 3</p> <p>Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and H-index.</p>	<p>The DNRF does not request citation-based metrics at any stage of assessment on the individual or center level but does not prevent anyone from providing bibliometric information as part of their self-assessment. The DNRF's position is that bibliometric information must be used at the relevant level of aggregation and must always be considered a supplement to qualitative assessment. The Foundation makes use of both peer review and interviews in its assessment procedures. The Foundation uses annotated publication lists for qualitative depth.</p>	<p>None – the DNRF considers its current practice to align well with the ARRA commitments.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Core commitment 4</p> <p>Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.</p>	<p>The DNRF does not use such rankings.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Supporting commitment 5</p> <p>Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.</p>	<p>The DNRF commits significant resources to promote responsible research assessment.</p>	<p>The DNRF will continue to commit the necessary resources, including for new initiatives, as described above.</p>	<p>Continually.</p>

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<p>Supporting Commitment 6</p> <p>Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.</p>	<p>DNRF assessment criteria, tools, and processes have been continually refined over three decades, with dialogue and peer review as cornerstones.</p>	<p>Based on the key priorities of the DNRF strategic priorities for 2026-2030, the DNRF will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explore more robust early stage assessment and monitoring. - develop continual monitoring processes with a focus on field-specific, rather than generic success criteria. 	<p>A new model for early-stage assessment will be tested in 2026.</p> <p>Monitoring processes will be continually assessed and improved. As a first step, in 2026, grant holders will be consulted about appropriate reporting.</p>
<p>Supporting Commitment 7</p> <p>Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.</p>	<p>In 2024-2025, the DNRF held dialogue with all centers on responsible research assessment, to inspire reflection at the Centers of Excellence and share good practice.</p>	<p>The DNRF will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensure that the lessons from dialogue will be fed back to the centers, along with the Foundation's action plan. - initiate bias training for the board and secretariat. - continue to communicate its assessment procedures widely, to ensure full transparency and learning across funding organizations. 	<p>Bias training and grant holder dialogue will be initiated in 2026.</p>
<p>Supporting Commitment 8</p> <p>Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.</p> <p>and</p> <p>Supporting Commitment 9</p> <p>Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.</p>	<p>The DNRF participates in the CoARA network of the Danish National Chapter (secretariat level).</p>	<p>The DNRF will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - continue participating in the CoARA network of the Danish National Chapter (secretariat level). - make this action plan available at the DNRF and CoARA websites. 	<p>The DNRF's CoARA action plan will be announced in 2026.</p>
<p>Supporting commitment 10</p> <p>Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.</p>	<p>Based on its recent evaluation, the Foundation knows that grant-holders consider the selection and assessment procedures sound and transparent, but the DNRF lacks systematic insights from rejected applicants.</p>	<p>The DNRF will seek feedback from rejected applicants regarding the Foundation's selection and assessment procedures.</p>	<p>Dialogue with rejected applicants will be initiated when the current call has been concluded in 2027.</p>

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